

Monitoring and investigating trafficking in cultural property: Achievements and Challenges
National Expert Roundtable, 21 to 22 September, Lviv

DAY 1	
0830-0900	Registration
0900-0930	<p>Opening and welcome (TBC – Ukraine official, Germany official, University of Lviv, UNODC)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introductions
0930-1030	<p>Session I: Setting the stage – International and national legal and regulatory framework</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Moderator: Ukraine PGO</u> – Case example to illustrate the discussion, Ukraine legislation overview • UNODC – international legal framework (UNTOC) + research – AE / KM • UNESCO – 1954 Convention and local situation- TBC • Electronic evidence and the legal possibilities of cultural property investigations (Andriy Melnyk, Lviv Ivan Franko National University; Roman Bily, Lviv State University of Internal Affairs) <p>Panel interventions (10 min per intervention) – 40 min Discussion, conclusions and recommendations - 20 min</p>
1030-1100	<i>Break</i>
1100-1215	<p>Session II: Setting the stage – Assessment of the situation (including the intersection between TCP and war crimes)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Moderator: Ministry of Culture</u> - Case example, the role of Ministry of Culture in the system of Ukraine cultural heritage protection – TBC • Violations in the field of cultural heritage protection from 24.02.22 to today. Fallacia accidentis (Mykhailo Gabrel, King Danylo University) • Cultural artifacts in the system of illegal business and criminal subculture (Oleg Pidkhomnyi, Ivan Franko National University of Lviv) • Cultural heritage of Ukraine: from local monuments to the global network (Iryna Kiyanka, Ivan Franko National University of Lviv) • International experience and national particularities of cultural heritage preservation (Ihor Boyko, Department of Theory and History of Culture, Ivan Franko National University of Lviv) <p>Panel interventions (10 min per intervention) – 50 min Discussion, conclusions and recommendations - 25 min</p>
1215-1400	<i>Lunch and side meetings</i>
1400-1530	<p>Session III: Identification/monitoring of cases of illicit trafficking of cultural property</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Moderator: Ivan Franko National University of Lviv-</u> Case example and methodology of cultural properties illegal markets risk-oriented research (Oleg Pidkhomnyi, Ivan Franko National University of Lviv) • Accounting of movable cultural heritage as a prerequisite for its protection in wartime conditions (Olesya Datsko, Department of Art Management, Lviv National Academy of Arts) • Database management systems in the field of cultural property protection and countering related crimes (INTERPOL +/- ICOM?) - TBC • Monitoring of cultural properties movements between museums from the occupied territories and the aggressor country (Iryna Revak, Lviv State University of Internal Affairs) • Search and return of cultural properties using ARO/AMO tools (Anton Chubenko, Research Institute of Public Law) • Expertise of art historians in the identification of cultural properties (Andriy Komarnitsky, art historian) – 10 mins

	Panel interventions (10 min per intervention) – 60 min Discussion, conclusions and recommendations - 30 min
1530-1600	<i>Break</i>
1600-1700	Final discussion, outcomes and conclusion of Day 1
DAY 2	
0900-0915	Welcome and recap of Day 1
0915-1000	<p>Session IV: National Law enforcement responses</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Moderator: Ukraine SSU</i> – case example, successes challenges, statistics, links with monitoring/identification • National Police - case example, successes challenges, statistics, links with monitoring/identification • State Border Guard State Border Guard/Customs? – case example, successes challenges, statistics, links with monitoring/identification <p>Panel interventions (10 min per intervention) – 30 min Discussion, conclusions and recommendations - 15 min</p>
1000-1030	<i>Break</i>
1030-1200	<p>Session V: Financial monitoring and investigation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Moderator: Ukraine FIU</i> – case example, etc – TBC • Using of art and antiques objects for the committing financial crimes’ (Oleksandr Hlushchenko, State Financial Monitoring Service of Ukraine) • Prospects and ways of cultural properties market intermediaries’ integration into Ukraine financial monitoring system under the conditions of martial law (Ruslana Martyniv, Ukraine Ministry of Finance (travel from Kyiv); Olena Ponomarenko, Ukraine Ministry of Finance) • The role of the financial monitoring system in the cultural properties markets risk management (Oleg Mainych, specialist in financial monitoring in the banking sector, postgraduate student of the Ivan Franko National University of Lviv) • Peculiarities of training cultural property market intermediaries in financial monitoring skills (Rostislav Marchuk, director of the Academy of Financial Monitoring) • UNODC - cooperation with Ukraine on illicit trafficking and related financial flows - TBC <p>Questions and discussion – 60 mins Conclusions and recommendations 30 mins</p>
1200-1330	<i>Lunch and side meetings</i>
1330-1500	<p>4 Breakout groups for formulation of actionable recommendations</p> <p>Themes to be determined during the event based on discussion but may include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Institutional mapping for coordination platform of TCP • Programmatic/policy priorities (capacity, cooperation, research, equipment etc) • Creation of network of experts to support TCP responses • Students - how to improve engagement and results, role of CS
1500-1530	<i>Break</i>
1530-1700	<p>Closing session – TBC</p> <p>Presentation of breakout group recommendations – 40 mins</p> <p>Discussion and agreement on outcomes, recommendations and next steps – 50 min</p>